

Mental Health of Cancer Caregivers in Relation to their Resilience

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Cancer is a highly challenging and fatal illness, and one of the many life-threatening diseases of the present time. Cancer is not only challenging for patients, but it also brings many serious difficulties into the lives of their loved ones and their caregivers. Therefore, the purpose of this review paper is to examine how psychological strength, such as resilience, affects the mental health of cancer caregivers. It also aims to review previous research findings that explain how resilience effects are important in psychological factors such as caregiving-related burden, depression, anxiety, fear, and quality of life. This review includes major research articles published between 2005 and 2025. Additionally, studies related to interventions aimed at enhancing resilience have been incorporated into this review paper. Caregivers play a crucial role in the treatment and care of cancer patients. While fulfilling their numerous caregiving responsibilities, they also face many personal, social, and financial challenges. However, several previous studies have found that when caregivers possess positive capacities such as resilience, they can maintain their own health more effectively and contribute positively to the patient's well-being. They are also able to perform their caregiving responsibilities more successfully. The findings indicate that caregivers with higher levels of resilience tend to have a better quality of life and experience lower levels of burden.

Keywords: Cancer caregivers, interventions, psychological health outcomes, resilience

Millions of people worldwide suffer from cancer. Because cancer does not affect just one specific organ, but impacts the entire bodily system. Hence, it is understood as a cluster of multiple interconnected diseases. Among the many defining features of cancer, a primary one is the unregulated proliferation of abnormal cells and their dissemination within the body. These abnormal cells invade the surrounding tissues and, in severe conditions, spread to other parts of the body through the lymphatic or circulatory systems. This process of spreading to various body parts is known as metastasis (National Cancer Institute, 2021). Cancer is not only a national but also a global public health problem. In terms of cancer incidence, India ranks second in Asia and third in the world (Mathur et al., 2025). In the present situation, it is necessary to know how this disease can be controlled and in what ways it can be prevented.

Cancer Caregivers

Caregivers, who are often family members. Play a vital role during

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We have no known conflict of interest to disclose.

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the cancer journey. This primarily includes coordinating medical care, consulting doctors, and providing physical assistance to the patient, and offering emotional support (Molassiotis & Wang, 2022). However, while fulfilling these responsibilities, caregivers frequently experience high levels of stress, anxiety, depression, and fatigue (Oechsle et al., 2019). Balancing caregiving responsibilities is extremely challenging. Balancing personal and professional roles is also quite challenging. For these reasons, caregivers often fail to pay attention to their own health and well-being, which severely affects their mental health and overall quality of life. In addition, emotional stress, financial pressure, and the fear of losing a loved one also affect them very seriously.

Cancer Caregivers' Psychological Health

Caregivers of cancer patients often experience a high caregiver burden. Caregiver burden has been defined by Given et al. (2001) as "it is a multidimensional biopsychosocial reaction resulting from an imbalance between the demands of caregiving and the caregiver's personal time, social roles, physical and emotional states, financial resources, and formal care resources, while they also fulfil multiple other roles." Such informal caregivers typically dedicate 18 to 33 hours per week to caring for their loved ones (Dionne-Odom et al., 2017; Trevino et al., 2018). According to Ge and Mordiffi (2017), approximately 35% of caregivers experience a high level of burden. Caregivers of advanced-stage cancer patients are often found to have a low quality of life (Ito & Tadaka, 2017). In addition, high levels of depression and anxiety are observed among these caregivers (Nipp et al., 2016). When caregivers possess psychologically positive attributes, they tend to have a better quality of life. Resilience is one such positive psychological trait. The practice and development of resilience enable caregivers to cope more effectively with caregiving-related stress and responsibilities.

Cancer Caregivers' Resilience

Deshields et al. (2016) defined resilience as “it is understood as a combination of mental skills and competencies that allow individuals to handle stressful experiences by drawing effectively on their internal and external resources”. Resilience is not one fixed characteristic; rather, it consists of multiple abilities and skills, such as managing one's emotions (Kay, 2016; Polizzi & Lynn, 2021; Troy & Mauss, 2011; Tugade & Fredrickson, 2007), problems-solving (Coşkun et al., 2014; Hou & Chen, 2024; Tugade & Fredrickson, 2007), optimism (Tainter & Taylor, 2014), self-efficacy (Hinz et al., 2019; Lafuenti et al., 2025), and social skills (Jiang et al., 2022).

Resilience enables individuals not only to cope with difficult circumstances but, at times, to move forward and grow through those situations. Through resilience, caregivers are not only able to avoid stress but also become capable of adapting to it effectively. Resilient individuals manage stress effectively through their proactive approach. For which they make use of both their personal strengths and the resources available in their environment (Alvord & Grados, 2005). Resilience is a multidimensional construct that includes cognitive, emotional, behavioral, and social components (Iacoviello & Charney, 2020).

Resilience, Burden, and Quality of Life

Üzar-Özçetin and Dursun (2020) revealed that resilience has both direct and indirect effects on caregivers' burden and their quality of life (QoL). Family caregivers with a lower level of resilience were found to experience greater caregiver burden and lower quality of life. Therefore, a high level of resilience among FCs may help to prevent caregiver burden and make it easier for them to adopt better coping strategies, thereby leading to a significant improvement in their quality of life. Likewise, previous research has shown a strong association between resilience and improved quality of life, along with reduced psychosocial distress (Kim et al., 2016; Lim et al., 2014). Individuals with high resilience can recover from severely unpleasant experiences because of their ability to adapt to difficult situations (Hwang et al., 2018; Rosenberg et al., 2014). Resilience is relevant in caregiving roles of different chronic illnesses (Cal et al., 2015; Coon, 2012; Ewen et al., 2015; Jin et al., 2023). Several research findings indicated that it is helpful to manage anxiety and depression (Dionne-Odom, 2021; Hwang et al., 2018; Palacio et al., 2018; Schumacher et al., 2014). Resilience is very supportive in the recovery of trauma (Alim et al., 2008; Nugent et al., 2014). Managing interpersonal relationships and achieving personal growth is the most important psychological factor (Gibbons et al., 2019; Lee et al., 2016; Liu et al., 2018; Luo et al., 2020; Palacio & Limonero, 2020; Pei et al., 2025). In addition, resilient caregivers have the strength to adopt healthier behaviours.

Resilience plays an important role in enhancing the capacity of informal caregivers to bear several caregiving-related burdens. Studies have shown that highly resilient caregivers of cancer patients were associated with lower levels of depression, better health, and reduced levels of caregiver burden (Karabekiroğlu et al., 2018; Palacio et al., 2018). A study resulted that resilience improves the quality of life and reduces emotional distress of cancer caregivers (Palacio et al., 2020). Research revealed that caregivers of advanced-stage cancer patients who had a low level of resilience experienced higher levels of caregiver burden (Van Roij et al., 2021). In contrast, caregivers with higher resilience reported low to moderate levels of

caregiver burden (Manzari et al., 2023). The study indicated that family members experiencing higher caregiver burden were generally relatively younger, more highly educated, and less aware of self-care practices (Van Roij et al., 2021). Røen et al. (2018) suggested that several factors contribute to enhancing resilience. These include the availability of palliative care, adequate information and effective communication about the illness, and a good relationship between the informal caregiver and the patient, among others. In the caregiving context, the analyzed studies indicate that resilience is a psychological factor that regulates and appropriately guides active coping, including emotional, problem-focused, and meaning-centered strategies, and helps reduce the negative effects arising from caregiving (Sivadasan & Bhuyan, 2025; Van der Hallen et al., 2020).

Techniques to Improve Resilience

Resilience-building interventions help the caregivers maintain good psychological health. Several types of resilience-related interventions help maintain emotional balance and develop a sense of control over adverse circumstances. Resilient persons have the strength to cope more effectively with various challenges (Friedberg & Malefakis, 2022). This review presents some highly effective techniques for developing and enhancing resilience. Coping strategies are a more effective technique to enhance resilience. Coping strategies play an important role in dealing with stressful situations and in emotion regulation (Booth & Neill, 2017). Problem-focused coping and emotion-focused coping contributed to the enhancement of resilience to exert control over situations, and encouraged positive thinking (Folkman & Moskowitz, 2004; Sivadasan & Bhuyan, 2025). A study was conducted on cancer caregivers' coping strategies, which resulted that both problem-focused coping and emotion-focused coping were associated with a lower level of caregiver burden (Tiwari et al., 2025). In contrast, dysfunctional coping strategies were associated with a higher level of caregiver burden (Chen et al., 2023; Dev et al., 2024; Tiwari et al., 2025). Thus, through regular practices of positive and healthy coping strategies, caregivers can enhance their resilience.

Good social support is also an important technique for enhancing resilience (Afita & Nuranasmita, 2023). Family, friends, or peer support groups consist of social support. Study indicated that caregivers who experienced less loneliness due to social support have higher levels of resilience (Southwick et al., 2016). Social support provides many emotional and instrumental resources that reduce the negative effects of stress (Sippel et al., 2015). Resilience also correlated with cancer patients and their caregivers' social support networks. If cancer patients and their caregivers have good social support, they demonstrate a greater level of resilience (Costa et al., 2017; Vartak, 2015).

Many studies focused on cognitive restructuring (cognitive reframing) techniques, which have contributed to caregivers' emotional adaptability, helping in finding positive aspects in difficult situations and deriving meaning from them (Harvey et al., 2019; Magdalena, 2022). And thus, it can also be helpful in increasing the overall resilience in cancer patients and their caregivers.

Some emotion regulation practices, such as mindfulness meditation, deep breathing, pranayama, and engaging in good hobbies, are very supportive in making a person emotionally resilient (Baghjari et al., 2017; Cleary et al., 2025; Kanthi et al.,

2022; Lincoln et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2021; Patel et al., 2018; Springstein & English, 2024). Engaging in physical exercise, physical activities, taking a balanced nutrition diet, engaging in good hobbies, following some relaxation techniques such as yoga nidra and JPMR (Jacobson Muscle Relaxation Technique), and adequate sleep can be helpful to maintain resilience of cancer caregivers (Cuthbert et al., 2018; Shin et al., 2020; Shivarama et al., 2024).

Discussion

Resilience is an extremely important psychological factor in the cancer journey. This is not only important for cancer patients but also for their caregivers and close ones. Resilient cancer caregivers can maintain their mental well-being, no matter how challenging the situation is. And they also experience a reduced sense of burden, depression, anxiety, stress, fear, and other related problems (Deshields et al., 2022; Seiler & Jenewein, 2019). This enables them to engage more effectively in treatment and move toward a better quality of life. Previous research has also shown that when cancer patients are resilient, their health improves, and, simultaneously, their caregivers' health remains better (Wang et al., 2021). Furthermore, if caregivers themselves are resilient, they can maintain their quality of life and overall well-being even in such stressful circumstances, and their resilience has a positive impact on patients as well. Therefore, programs that address both the patient and the caregiver together, known as dyadic interventions, are essential. Dyadic resilience-related interventions are highly beneficial for the overall healthcare system. This review paper finds that interventions to enhance resilience are highly effective in improving health.

Limitations and Future Research Directions

Future assessments of research should consider the limitations of the current review. First, the review paper is a form of narrative review; therefore, a systematic literature review can be conducted on this topic in the future. Second, this paper focuses only on the health of cancer caregivers, which represents a one-sided approach, as the condition of the patient also affects the health of the caregivers. Therefore, future research should also examine how the health of cancer patients and their caregivers mutually affect each other. Third, there is a significant need for research in this area that uses dyadic interventions to enhance the resilience of both patients and their caregivers simultaneously. Therefore, interventions should be designed to be suitable for both patients and their caregivers and to enhance the resilience of both.

Conclusion

In summary, resilience helps individuals maintain a positive outlook and constructive thinking in the face of adversity. This research paper highlights an important yet often overlooked aspect of the caregiving experience. In which important issues related to caregivers' resilience and mental health have been focused on. This paper sets the path for methods and interventions focused on increasing resilience among cancer caregivers by emphasizing their utility.

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Received December 24, 2025

Revision received January 13, 2025

Accepted January 16, 2025